

EXPLORING DEPLOYABLE CONFIGURATIONS USING INTERLEAVED COMPOSITE WITH SHAPE MEMORY CAPABILITY

H.A. Maples¹, P. Robinson², B. Zhang², A. Bismarck^{1,3}, W. Li² and C. Burgstaller⁴

¹ Polymer and Composite Engineering (PaCE) group, Department of Material Chemistry, University of Vienna, Währinger Strasse 42, A-1090 Wien, Austria

Email: alexander.bismarck@univie.ac.at, henry.maples@univie.ac.at

² The Composites Centre, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, South Kensington Campus, London SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

Email: bohao.zhang12@imperial.ac.uk, p.robinson@imperial.ac.uk

³ Polymer and Composite Engineering (PaCE) group, Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, South Kensington Campus, London SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

Email: a.bismarck@imperial.ac.uk

⁴ Transfercenter für Kunststofftechnik (TCKT), Franz-Fritsch-Straße 11, A-4600, Wels, Austria

Keywords: Carbon fibre/epoxy composites, Interleaving, Shape memory, Deployable structures

ABSTRACT

An interleaved composite which exhibits shape memory capability controlled by heating has been developed. Trials of this material have been conducted to investigate the potential of using the interleaved composite for deployable structures. This paper reports on an investigation of the shape memory performance of a deployable spring made of the interleaved composite in tension. It is shown that the spring was easily re-shaped to a straight shape with little force and exhibited an excellent shape recovery (99.5%) upon re-heating. This spring may be suitable as a shape memory actuator for space applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

An interleaved composite has been developed in Imperial College London which exhibits the stiffness control [1-3] and shape memory capabilities [4, 5] on heating. The shape memory mechanism of this composite which consists of carbon fibre/epoxy laminae and the polystyrene interleaf is shown in Figure 1. When heated to 120°C (this temperature is beyond the glass transition temperature of the interleaf material), the stiffness of the interleaf is significantly reduced, so that the composite plies can slide relative to each other. At this temperature, the laminate can be easily re-shaped in bending as shown here. This temporary shape is retained if held in this shape while cooling down, as the flexural stiffness of the laminate is restored. Upon re-heating to 120°C, the laminate recovers towards its original shape due to the release of the stored elastic strain in the composite plies.

Figure 1: Concept of the shape memory capability of the interleaved composite.

Trials of this composite have been conducted to investigate the potential of using this composite for deployable structures [4]. Figure 2 shows the deployment process of a deployable box section made of the interleaved composite. It is shown that the box section, consisting of the interleaved composite adhesively bonded with non-interleaved carbon fibre/epoxy laminate (i.e. no shape memory capability), deployed to the square shape within 150 seconds.

Figure 2: A sequence of frames from the deployment video of a deployable structure using the interleaved composite [4].

The trial in Figure 2 used the flexural shape memory of the interleaved composite to return the corners of the box section to 90° angles. In this paper the use of the same material to produce linear actuation (rather than angular actuation) is investigated. The interleaved composite is manufactured in the form of a spring and its shape memory performance in tension is explored. FE modelling is also used to investigate the re-shaping capability of the spring.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Materials

A carbon fibre/epoxy composite (TS300/914, thickness of 0.125 mm, purchased from Hexcel) was used in the current work. Polystyrene, supplied as films from TCKT, was selected as the interleaf material (0.1 mm thickness). The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polystyrene is 87°C measured in DSC and this is lower than the T_g of the cured epoxy matrix at 180°C. Basic mechanical properties of these materials are shown in Table 1.

Materials	Property	Value
Hexcel TS300/914 carbon epoxy composite	E_1 , GPa	135
	E_2 , GPa	8.5
	ν_{12}	0.32
	G_{12} , GPa	3.42
Styrolution polystyrene (120°C) (isotropic)	E , GPa	0.08
	ν_{12}	0.3
	G_{12} , GPa	0.03

Table 1: The properties of the materials.

2.2 Specimen design and manufacture

A 0° unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy lamina bonded with polystyrene interleaf on both surfaces was manufactured using corrugated moulds in the sine wave profile. The mould possesses a wavelength (λ) of 60 mm and an amplitude (A) of 5 mm. The panel was cured in an autoclave, following the manufacturer's recommendation. Six carbon strips (250 mm long and 20 mm wide) were prepared from the panel. They were stacked together and were then post-cured in a hot press at 120°C for an hour to form a laminated spring. Glass fibre end-tabs were adhesively bonded on both ends of the spring. Figure 3 shows the post-cured spring ready to be tested.

Figure 3: A photograph of the post-cured shape memory spring made of the interleaved composites.

2.3 Shape memory test

A uniaxial tension test was conducted to investigate the shape memory performance of the spring. It was mounted on a tension fixture on an Instron universal test machine (Instron 5985 fitted with a 5kN load cell) in an environmental chamber.

The spring was initially heated to 120°C in the chamber and then kept at this temperature for 15 minutes. The spring was subjected to tension at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until a rapid increase in applied load indicating that the spring was almost stretched. After this, the spring was held at this shape while cooling down to room temperature. It was then removed from the jaws of the machine to measure any springback in specimen length. The 'straightened' spring was mounted on the fixture at the upper end and the lower end was kept free. The specimen was then re-heated to 120°C and the shape recovery process was videoed using a Pentax camera.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

FE modelling was performed to investigate the re-shaping performance of the interleaved spring subjected to a uniaxial tension test at elevated temperature. The spring was simplified to a unit cell consisting of a layer of carbon fibre/epoxy composite containing a polystyrene interleaf. The spring was assigned the properties of the materials mentioned in section 2.1.

A 2-dimensional plane stress model of the interleaved composite spring was developed, as shown in Figure 4. Initially a single lamina of a carbon fibre/epoxy with a polystyrene interleaf on each interface was modelled. The composite ply was assigned the orthotropic properties shown in Table 1 for the elevated temperature state. For the polystyrene, the elevated-temperature isotropic properties shown in Table 1 were used.

Figure 4: The 2D model of the interleaved composite spring showing the mesh geometry through the thickness.

The composite ply was meshed with two-dimensional, 4-node, plane stress elements. Typically, two elements through the thickness of the composite ply were used. The polystyrene interleaf was meshed with two-dimensional, plane stress, 3-node triangular elements.

Node-to-node periodic constraints were applied at between the top surface of the polystyrene interleaf and the bottom surface of the carbon fibre/epoxy so that the vertical displacement at corresponding node is identical on the lower surface. Horizontal support conditions were applied at the left end of the model.

The specimen was loaded with a horizontal displacement at the right hand end shown in Figure 4 to extend the spring. A general, static solution including non-linear geometry was used for this case.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows the recorded load-displacement response of the spring subjected to a tension test at 120°C. It can be seen that the force was below 50 N upto a 12 mm displacement, but increased rapidly when the spring became close to straight. The FE modelling results shows a similar rapid increase of the applied load when the spring was fully stretched.

Figure 5: The load-displacement curves of the spring subjected to a uniaxial tension test at 120°C.

During the tension test some debonding of the composite plies was observed (See insert photograph in Figure 6). Following testing, the spring was removed after loading from the jaws to measure any springback in specimen length. Very little springback in the length (about 0.1%) was observed, as the spring is in its high stiffness state at room temperature. Figure 6 shows the configuration of the spring in its 'straightened' state.

Figure 6: The photograph of the 'straightened' spring removed from the test machine and debonding of the composite plies captured during the tension test.

The straightened spring was re-heated to 120°C in the environmental chamber to investigate the shape recovery capability. Figure 7 shows a series of still images from the shape recovery video. Due to the limitation of the camera, only the gauge section of the spring was observed. It can be seen that the spring rapidly recovered towards the original shape and around 80% of the shape recovery was achieved within the first 100s. However, the recovery rate slowed down due to the viscoelastic behaviour of the polystyrene interleaf. Further work will be performed to predict the recovery time using FE modelling.

Figure 7: The frames from the shape recovery video of the ‘straight’ spring at 120°C.

Figure 8 plots the recovered aspect ratio versus time response of the spring during shape recovery phase. It confirms that the deployment of the spring at elevated temperature was initially rapid. However, it can be seen that a long time is required to fully recover the original shape.

Figure 8: The measured aspect ratio versus time plot of the shape recovery of the spring.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A shape memory spring structure made of interleaved carbon fibre/epoxy composite was developed to investigate its shape memory capability in tension. It has been shown that the structure can be readily extended at elevated temperature and that it retains this new shape after cooling to room temperature. On re-heating the spring returns to its original shape. FE modelling also confirmed the re-shaping capability of the structure. This spring has potential as a linear actuator for space applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Tridech, H.A. Maples, P. Robinson, and A. Bismarck, High performance composites with active stiffness control, *Applied Materials and Interfaces*, **5**, 2013, pp. 9111-9119 (doi: 10.1021/am402495n).
- [2] H.A. Maples, S. Wakefield, P. Robinson, and A. Bismarck, High performance carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites with controllable stiffness, *Composite Science and Technology*, **105**, 2014, pp. 134-143 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.09.008).
- [3] P. Robinson, H. Maples, O. Gaite, S. Smith and A. Bismarck, Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites with variable stiffness for use in morphing aerostructures, *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Composite Materials 2013, Montreal, Canada, July 28-August 2, 2013*.
- [4] P. Robinson, A. Bismarck, B. Zhang, and H. Maples, Deployable, shape memory carbon fibre composites without shape memory constituents. *Composites Science and Technology*, **145**, 2017, pp. 96-104.
- [5] P. Robinson, A. Bismarck, B. Zhang and H.A. Maples, Exploring the potential of controllable stiffness hybrid composites, *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composite Materials 2014, Seville, Spain, June 22-26, 2014*.